

Effect of Internal Control Structures on Financial Management in National Public Secondary School in Cost Region, Kenya

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Abstract

Financial resources are crucial to the success of any business. Without revenue, no company has ever succeeded. As a result, financial management must be considered by institutions, enterprises, organizations, and commercial entities in order to improve their performance and, more importantly, to reduce their exposure to financial risks. The educational sector's growth and development are determined by how well income is managed. Financial management is concerned with an organization's decisions on how to raise cash, how to manage financial resources through revenue controls, and how to allocate revenue resources wisely. It is critical to any organization's success. The government of Kenya has put in place internal control system to ensure that the funds invested in education are used for the right purpose. However, accountability and management is still wanting in some national public secondary schools. The main purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of internal control structures on financial management in national public secondary school in Cost region, Kenya. Specific objectives being to establish the effect of control environmental system on financial management in national public secondary school in Kenya and to analyze the effect of control activities system on financial management in national public secondary school in Kenya. The study was carried out in 12 national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya. The study was guided by financial control theory. Survey research design was used on population consisting of 12 principals, bursars 12 and 12 BOM chairs. Data were collected by use of questionnaires. Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data collected. Inferential statistics comprised of Correlation analysis, ANOVA, regression analysis. The study found that there exist a positive, strong and statistically significant association between control environment and financial management. Similarly, the study found that there exist a positive, strong and statistically significant association between control activities and financial management. The study found that the factors under study which were control environment and control activities had a positive and strong relationship ($R = 0.516$) with financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya. Moreover, the factors studied were found to explain 51.6% of financial management in public secondary schools in Coast region, in Kenya ($R^2 = 0.516$). The regression coefficient results revealed that a change by 1 unit in financial management was as a result of changes by 0.470 unit in control environment and 0.462 unit in control activities while holding (0.109) constant. It was revealed that control environment and control activities significantly influenced financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya. The study therefore concluded that there exists a positive and significant relationship between control environment and financial management in national public secondary schools in in Coast region, Kenya. This implies that when control environment improves, financial management will improve.

Keywords: Internal Control Structures, Financial Management

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Resources for an organization's finances are crucial. Without adequate financial resources, no organization has ever been successful (Kimani & Munge, 2017). Therefore, financial management must be taken into account by institutions, enterprises, organizations, and commercial entities in order to improve their performance and, more importantly, reduce their exposure to financial risks. The management of funds has an impact on the expansion and growth of the educational sector. The decisions made by an organization regarding where to obtain funding, how to govern financial resources through financial controls, how to allocate financial resources wisely, and accountability measures are all part of financial management. It is essential to every organization's success. Financial management is justified by the need to increase proper use of the finances and raise money for both short- and long-term purpose.

The funds for educational institutions are used for their regular operations and activities. Secondary school principals and administrators are responsible for creating the school budget in order to meet the goals of the institution, with competent financial management being of particular importance (Maronga, Weda, & Kengere, 2018). (Sharma, 2011). In an effort to improve school management, many nations have decentralized financial resource management. Despite the emphasis placed on financial resources to bring about desperately needed reform and service delivery, it is highlighted that these resources are occasionally mismanaged and misused by those in control (Kimani & Munge, 2017).

One of the main causes of poor internal control systems is overspending or under spending, which can result in the embezzlement and improper management of school funds (Mito & Simatwa, 2019). The necessity to investigate the financial management in educational institutions and provide proper training for school heads on financial management is prompted by components of these internal control systems that regulate the environment and control activities, among others.

Internal control is a crucial process that involves leaders and staff members acting continuously to ensure that an organization's goals are met in terms of operational effectiveness and efficiency, trustworthy financial reporting, the security of state assets, and compliance with laws, regulations, and policies that are strictly followed in an educational setting. As a public institution, schools are tasked with promoting compulsory education and provide educational services to all pupils. According to accounting standards, the principal must inform the School Committee and Government of the school's financial statements. As a result, financial accounting standards are applied to each report that the school administration creates. For those who use the education services, in particular, this ensures public accountability. Additionally, managing funding sources and developing a suitable control mechanism for financial decision-making are also goals of financial management in educational organizations in order to achieve a transparent, accountable, and successful institution. All stakeholders would have better social accountability thanks to sound financial management (Aramide, Fasilat, Mustapha, & Bashir, 2015). Many state governments have internal control mechanisms in place to regulate how education money are used. Internal control systems are a method that a board of management and other staff members of a business use to provide reliable assurance that objectives will be achieved. It plays a weighty role in pinpointing and hindering deception and protecting the organization's assets, both physical and immaterial (Institute of Policy Analysis and Research, 2014).

Making sure that money is used as effectively and efficiently as possible is the main goal of financial management (Ogbonnaya, 2020). The author makes the case that because resources are limited, educational administrators must make the best use of what they have to accomplish institutional goals. Lack of adequate training for educational leaders, carelessness on the part of school financial clerks, and other factors, among others, fuel poor management of funds in institutions in Nigeria. Poor management of available funds leads to embezzlement, diverting funds away from prioritized projects, and misappropriations. On the same state poor state of schools in Benue State in Nigeria was as a result of financial management issues such as the inability to generate revenue internally and misuse of available resources (Bua & Adzongo, 2018).

On the local perspective, various scholars have documented the theme of financial management of the education sector in Kenya precisely secondary schools. According to a study by Kimani & Munge, (2017), school management and school heads are responsible for demonstrating accountability and transparency and delegating financial responsibility. The scholars noted that loss of funds was common in secondary schools in Kenya.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Accountability's primary goal is to promote responsible behavior among students as a condition for creating a trustworthy and good school (Mardiasmo, 2017). Accountability for all aspects of management to the community is expected of school administrators. Accountability includes not only the learning process but also budgeting and product quality. The decline in financial management irregularities can be used to gauge financial accountability. The management can answer for the source of funds, its amount, and its distribution (Haryanto, 2017). The school community and general public will trust the financially responsible management. Many academics have written about the issue of financial management in Kenya's secondary schools specifically. The management of schools and school heads are in charge of displaying accountability and transparency and assigning financial responsibility, per a study by Kimani and Munge (2017). The researchers observed that financial losses were frequent in Kenya's secondary schools.

There are still questions about financial responsibility in some public secondary schools; according to a report by the Ethics and Anti-Corruption Commission, thirty percent (30%) of the money used to subsidize secondary education could not be accounted for by the various school principals. Senior Ministry of Education officials and head teachers were found to have misappropriated Kenyan shillings 4.2 billion from donors and Kenyan taxpayers, according to an audit report by the ministry of finance, which caused the international development partners funding free primary education to withdraw from the project (Transparency International Kenya, 2014). Despite the internal control procedures the Kenyan government has put in place, these misappropriations continue to occur.

1.3 General Objective

To evaluate the influence of internal control system on financial management in national public Secondary Schools in Coast region, Kenya

1.3.1 Specific Objectives

i. To establish the influence of control environment on financial management in national public Secondary Schools in Coast region, Kenya

ii. To examine the influence of control activities on financial management in national public Secondary Schools in Coast region, Kenya

1.4 Research Hypotheses

HO1a: There is no significant influence of control environment on financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya.

HO1b: There is significant influence of control environment on financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya.

HO2a: There is no significant influence of control activities on financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya.

HO2b: There is significant influence of control activities on financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This part presents a review of theories of financial management and this includes theory of financial control.

2.1: Theory of Financial Control

Ostman advanced the philosophy of financial control (2009). The idea views human personal functions—both current and future—as its central point of reference. According to this approach, financial instruments for companies should focus on their current and potential uses. Additionally, it stipulates that discussions about payments, financial instruments, accounting, control models, economic calculations, and similar matters, both inside and outside of the organization, should take into account both internal and external factors. From the perspective of financial control, it is observed that establishing the connections between diverse activities and financial processes is a broad and fundamental issue (Ostman, 2009).

The idea of financial controls for organizations naturally focuses on the companies, allowing for many latitudinal perspectives on them. The first relates to the roles played by people in the actions and results produced by organizations. The second is concerned with the organization, activities, and transactions that different parties engage in with one another. The third section deals with control systems, which are recurrent processes and techniques used to link current and future functions to resources on both an internal and external level. The aforementioned financial control tools are said to be essential for both smaller economic systems and organizations as a whole. The fourth and last area illustrates the specific processes of individual organizations for certain issues. The theory further states that structure and financial control system works together (Ostman, 2009). The financial control theory is very pertinent to the present study in that it enables the understanding of financial controls that are an aspect of financial management in public secondary schools in Kenya.

2.2 Control Environment

The control of an environment where people may conduct their activities and efficiently perform control tasks is known as the control environment. The set of rules, procedures, and frameworks known as the control environment serve as the foundation for implementing internal control throughout the entire organization. The board of directors and senior management set the tone for internal control, including expected norms of conduct, at the top of the organization. Management raises standards across the board in the organization (Oduol, 2017). Control environment is a component of internal control. This includes many factors, such as integrity, ethics, employees' competence and management philosophy in the organization. All of these are components that become the foundation of other components to build a system of financial internal control (COSO, 2005).

International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions (INTOSAI) states that control environment will color an organization, influence the control consciousness of its employees. This is the foundation for all other internal control components that provide discipline and structure. The elements of control environment are personal and professional integrity and ethics of management and staff, including supportive attitude towards internal control throughout the organization at all times; commitment to competence; leadership role model; organizational structure and human resources policies and practices.

2.3 Control activities

The practices and regulations that help ensure that management directions are successfully executed are known as control activities. They offer a way to deal with the various risks that could prevent the organization from achieving its goals. In essence, control actions are set up in response to dangers that are visible. Management instructions are carried out through the use of control activities as rules and procedures. They aid in making sure that the required steps are made to address risks preventing the entity from achieving its objectives. All levels and functions of the organization engage in control activities. Authorization, confirmations, reconciliations, reviews of operational performance, security of assets, and separation of roles are only a few examples of the various control activities (Gbegi, Adebisi & Makurdi, 2015).

Policies, procedures, and practices that are designed to enhance risk management approach make up control activities. Separation of roles, verification, reconciliation, and physical asset security are all types of special control activities. The policies are designed to ensure that management directives are carried out (COSO, 1992). According to INTOSAI (1992) control activities are policies and procedures to face risk and to realize the objectives of the entity. To be effective, control activities must function accordingly and be consistent with the plan within the period, and spend cost effectively, comprehensively, reasonably and directly related to control objectives. They occur throughout the organization, at all levels and functions. Detective and preventive control activities cover (INTOSAI,1992) such as authorization and approval procedures; separation of duties (authorizing, processing, recording, reviewing); access to resources and records; verification; reconciliation; review on operational performance; review on operations, processes and activities and supervision (assigning, reviewing and approving, guiding and training).

2.4 The influence of Internal Control System on Financial management

Responsibility follows naturally from the interaction between the agent and the principle. An agency relationship is a contract in which the owner (principal) delegated decision-making power to the business or organization (agent). The framework for accountability is agency theory. The responsibility to disclose required information, including financial information, or calculations (reckoning), based on activities done by the organization, is known as financial accountability (Gray et al., 2014). Financial accountability refers to the duty of the trustee (government) to furnish, present, report, and disclose all of their responsibilities to the mandate giver (public), who has the right to do so (Mardiasmo, 2012). Accountability requires organization to comply with all applied laws and ethical standards; the mission of organization, personnel and accounting policies; to protect members' rights; to prepare and submit annual financial statements accordingly and to make the reports available to all board members and all public members. The development and preservation of organizational internal control will help ensure accountability (Andrew Cuomo, 2005). The basic idea of control in public sector is to ensure that an organization operates in line with legal, policies and prescribed objectives. Control system provides assurance that financial management system works properly. Furthermore, control and accountability are mechanisms that interact each other (OECD, 2005).

Ray and Pany (2011) in Mawanda (2008) state that control activities as a component of internal control is a policy and procedure that help ensure that management directives are implemented. Control activities within an organization basically consist of: performance assessment (compare actual performance with budget, forecast and performance of the previous period), information processing (necessary for checking the accuracy, completeness, and authorization of transactions), physical control (which is necessary to provide security recordkeeping and other assets), and separation of duties (where one should not deal with all aspects of the transaction

from beginning to end). Effective internal controls promote management effectiveness (Otieno, 2013). An organization manages its activities using an internal control system to ensure effectiveness, efficiency, dependable financial responsibility, and compliance with laws and regulations (Aramide and Bashir, 2015). An Nissa Surya Sumunar has researched the connection between internal control and the application of excellent financial management in the sense of accountability (2014). It demonstrates a helpful connection and substantial impact. Godfrey also researches the same subject (2013). The outcome demonstrates that the integrity of the administrators and the employees' commitment to ethics have a significant impact on the state of the internal

control environment in regencies. However, integrity is the ground for good governance in most organizations. There's a strong positive relationship between internal control environment and financial accountability in which internal control environment is a strong predictor for financial accountability. The findings of Aramide & Bashir (2015) show that internal control system positively and significantly realize a good financial accountability.

2.5: Conceptual framework

Figure 2.1 Conceptual framework

CHAPTER THREE**RESEARCH METHODOLOGY****3.1 Research Design**

For this study, a descriptive survey research design was chosen. The variables in this study, which sought to determine the relationship between internal control systems and financial management, made the design the most suitable choice.

3.2 Target Population

The target population for this study was 12 National Public schools consisting of; 12 principals, 12 bursars and 12 BOM chairs.

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

Primary data was collected through the use of questionnaires. Closed-ended questions were used. Closed-ended questions were used because they are easy to administer and evaluate, they are also cost-effective in terms of time and money. Secondary data was collected through analysis of parameters.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

Primary data was collected by the researcher with the help of a research assistant where questionnaires were distributed to the sampled national public secondary schools. A period one month was allowed for filling up the questionnaires. The questionnaires were then collected back after one month.

3.5 Data Analysis and Presentation

The data collected was processed and cleaned and analyzed using SPSS. Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data collected. Inferential statistics used to measure the relationship between variables comprised of Pearson Product moment correlation for correlation analysis and Simple and multiple regression analysis. Data was presented using tables, charts, and graphs.

3.6 Multiple Regression Analysis

An equation was derived as a basis for the estimation and measure of the proportion of variance between the dependent variable and independent variables. Regression analysis, which determines the relationship between variables, was used to find out the connection between the independent variables (Control environment and Control activities) and the dependent variable (Financial management).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Where

Y= Financial management, X_1 =Control environment and X_2 =Control activities

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Response rate

The number of respondents that filled out questionnaires completely and as directed, divided by the total number of respondents who make up the sample group, is referred to as the response rate (Holbrook, Kronsick & Pfent, 2008). The response rate offers important information about the accuracy of the data gathered. In this study, 36 questionnaires which were divided into three for BOM, bursars and principals were issued to the sampled respondents (BOM, principals and bursars). All the 36 questionnaires were successfully filled and returned. Therefore, response rate was 100%.

4.2 Inferential statistics analysis

Correlation analysis was employed to illustrate the existing relationship between the independent variable (Control environment and control activities) and the dependent variable (financial management). In addition, multiple regression analysis was used to ascertain the extent to which the factors under study influenced financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region.

4.2.1 Influence of control environment on Financial Management

The correlation findings in respect to the influence of internal control system (control environment and activities) on financial management are illustrated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Pearson Correlations

Variables		Financial management	Control environment	Control activities
Financial management	Pearson Correlation	1	.645**	.661**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	36	36	36
Control environment	Pearson Correlation	.645**	1	.655**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	36	36	36
Control activities	Pearson Correlation	.661**	.655**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	36	36	36

The study found that there existed a positive, strong and statistically significant association between control environment and financial management ($r = 0.645$; $p < 0.05$). As control environment became more effective, financial management in national public secondary schools

In coast region was enhanced. It was argued that national public secondary schools were able to carry out analysis and oversight composition of BOM and more so adhered to the laid down internal control system BOM status and hence were able to set realistic control environment. The foregoing enhanced financial management. Similarly, the study found that there existed a positive, strong and statistically significant association between control activities and financial management ($r = 0.661$; $p < 0.05$).

4.2.2: Regression Analysis for Overall Model

The influence of the factors investigated which were control environment and control activities on financial management of national public secondary schools was evaluated. In addition, the study established the combined influence of these factors on financial management in national public secondary schools. The results are presented in model summary table 4.2, ANOVA table 4.3 and coefficients table 4.4.

4.2.2.1: Model summary

The study noted that the factors under study which were control environment and control activities had a positive and strong relationship ($R = 0.516$) with financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya as shown in table 4.2. Moreover, the factors studied were found to explain 51.6% of financial management in public secondary schools in Coast region, in Kenya ($R^2 = 0.516$). And as such 48.4% of financial management in the schools was as a result of other factors not investigated in the study. The findings underscored the importance of control environment and control activities in managing finances in national public secondary schools in Coast region.

Table 4.2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.718 ^a	.516	.486	.82226

ANOVA

The ANOVA results showed in Table 4.3 indicated that the influence of control environment and control activities on financial management was significant ($F = 17.574$; $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the two factors investigated by the study were crucially important in enhancing financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region.

Table 4.3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.764	2	11.882	17.574	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.311	33	.676		
	Total	46.076	35			

Regression coefficient

The regression coefficient results revealed that a change by 1 unit in financial management was as a result of changes by 0.470 unit in control environment and 0.462 unit in control activities while holding (0.109) constant. It was revealed that control environment ($t = 2.318$; $p < 0.05$) and control activities ($t = 2.605$; $p < 0.05$) significantly influenced financial management in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya.

Table 4.4: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.109	.513		.213	.833
Control environment	.470	.203	.372	2.318	.027
Control activities	.462	.177	.418	2.605	.014

CHAPTER FIVE**CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS****5.1 Conclusions****5.1.1 Influence of Control Environment on Financial Accountability**

This study concludes that there exists a positive and significant relationship between control environment and financial management in national public secondary schools in in Coast region, Kenya. This implies that when control environment improves, financial management will improve.

5.1.2 Influence of Control Activities on Financial management

This study further concludes that there exists a positive and significant relationship between control activities and financial accountability in national public secondary schools in Coast region, Kenya. This implies that when control activities improve, financial accountability will improve.

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